

Damage evolution law in the framework of continuum damage mechanics for UD composites

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1 Introduction

Continuum damage mechanics (CDM) was introduced to deal with the progressive nature of failure in composites decades ago [1-3]. Early development of CDM has been concentrated on the damage representation, i.e. mathematical description of damage as a continuum. In a series of publications of Talreja [1-3], a rational approach was proposed. The development and the state-of-the-art of CDM has been reviewed in a recent paper [4] where the rationality of Talreja's CDM approach was appraised and the inconsistencies in other *ad-hoc* approaches have been revealed. However, in Talreja's CDM, the damage representation introduced a large number of damage related material constants (DRMCs). In [4], an attempt has also been made to determine some of the DRMCs involved in the damage representation. Use has been made of a series of ideal experiments. It has been found that in the case of a single array of cracks of common orientation in a UD composite, seven out of eight DRMCs can be determined and expressed in terms of conventional elastic properties of the virgin material. The remaining eighth DRMC can be determined through numerical experiments. This has closed an account on the development of the CDM representation, at least, for this specific mode of damage.

The present paper is to carry on with the work as in [4] in a rational manner and to extend the development to damage evolution by obtaining the damage driving forces from the derivatives of the Helmholtz free energy with respect to the damage variable.

With the damage evolution so described, a complete integrated CMD framework will be obtained. It will be presented.

2 Damage Variable, Irreducible Integrity bases and Helmholtz Free Energy

For planar cracks (microscopic in size and massive in number), it is often convenient to employ a vector damage variable to describe the damage [1-3], with the orientation of the vector coincident with the normal to the crack surface and the magnitude indicating the extent of the damage.

As commonly assumed, UD composites are transversely isotropic materials. For problems involving a second order tensor (strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$) and vector (damage $\boldsymbol{\nu}$) as the state variables in such a material, the irreducible invariant integrity [13] bases up to second order are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &= \varepsilon_1 \\
 I_2 &= \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \\
 I_3 &= 2\varepsilon_2^2 + \varepsilon_4^2 + 2\varepsilon_3^2 \\
 I_4 &= \varepsilon_5^2 + \varepsilon_6^2 \\
 I_5 &= \nu_1 \\
 I_6 &= \nu_2\varepsilon_6 + \nu_3\varepsilon_5 \\
 I_7 &= 2\nu_2\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_6 + \nu_2\varepsilon_4\varepsilon_5 + \nu_3\varepsilon_4\varepsilon_6 + 2\nu_3\varepsilon_3\varepsilon_5 \\
 I_8 &= \nu_2^2 + \nu_3^2 \\
 I_9 &= \nu_2^2\varepsilon_2 + \nu_2\nu_3\varepsilon_4 + \nu_3^2\varepsilon_3
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Obviously, each base is invariant under coordinate transformations corresponding to a rotation about axis-1, the transformation coincides with the material symmetry, the transverse isotropy. With this set of integrity bases, the Helmholtz free energy in terms of a Taylor series can be expressed as:

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{l} A_1 I_1^2 + A_2 I_1 I_2 + A_3 I_1^2 I_5^2 + A_4 I_1 I_3 I_6 + A_5 I_1^2 I_8 + A_6 I_1 I_9 + A_7 I_1 I_2 I_5^2 + A_8 I_1 I_2 I_8 \\ + B_1 I_2^2 + B_2 I_2 I_5^2 + B_3 I_2 I_3 I_6 + B_4 I_2^2 I_8 + B_5 I_2 I_9 \\ + C_1 I_3 + C_2 I_3 I_5^2 + C_3 I_3 I_8 \\ + D_1 I_4 + D_2 I_4 I_5^2 + D_3 I_4 I_8 \\ + E_1 I_5 I_7 \\ + F_1 I_6^2 \\ + G_1 I_5^2 + G_2 I_8 \end{array} \right) + O_2(\varepsilon, \mathbf{v}) \quad (2)$$

where the constant term (0th order) has been omitted as it will not make any contribution to the constitutive relationship to be established. The first order terms in strains should be included if initial stresses or strains are involved in the problem but they have been omitted here for the simplicity of the present discussion. The terms involving the components of the damage variable must be in an even order. This implies that changing the sense of the damage vector will not result in any change in terms of the state of damage. This is because crack surfaces are always paired, opposite to each other, and the damage vector can be perpendicular to either of the crack surfaces. All terms of higher orders than the second, including the coupling terms have been encapsulated in $O_2(\varepsilon, \mathbf{v})$ which will be neglected subsequently under the assumption of small strain and small damage.

3 Constitutive Relationship

The deformation process involving damage must satisfy the second law of thermodynamics (increasing entropy) to reflect its irreversible nature. The following constraint is obtained as a necessary condition for this consideration [12]

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \quad (3)$$

This results in the constitutive relationship for the damaged material [4]

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = (\mathbf{C}^0 + \mathbf{C}^1) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{C}^0 is the stiffness of the virgin material and \mathbf{C}^1 represents the increment of the stiffness due to damage. (4) above gives the stress, strain and damage relationship as governed by the law of thermodynamics.

When the stiffnesses \mathbf{C}^0 and \mathbf{C}^1 are expressed explicitly, they involve a lot of material properties, in terms of the coefficients in (2). Given the transverse isotropy of the virgin material, \mathbf{C}^0 only involves 5 independent material properties and they can be readily expressed in terms of familiar terms

of Young's moduli, shear moduli and Poisson's ratio.

$$\mathbf{C}^0 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1-\nu_{23}^0}{\Delta^0} E_1^0 & \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{\Delta^0} E_2^0 & \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{\Delta^0} E_2^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{\Delta^0} E_2^0 & \frac{1-\nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0}{(1+\nu_{23}^0) \Delta^0} E_2^0 & \frac{\nu_{23}^0 + \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0}{(1+\nu_{23}^0) \Delta^0} E_2^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}^0}{\Delta^0} E_2^0 & \frac{\nu_{23}^0 + \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0}{(1+\nu_{23}^0) \Delta^0} E_2^0 & \frac{1-\nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0}{(1+\nu_{23}^0) \Delta^0} E_2^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23}^0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12}^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12}^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta^0 = 1 - \nu_{23}^0 - 2\nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0$, $\nu_{21}^0 = \frac{E_2^0}{E_1^0} \nu_{12}^0$ and

$$G_{23}^0 = \frac{E_2^0}{2(1+\nu_{23}^0)}. \quad (6)$$

However, even under the restriction on the form of damage of a single array of microcracks giving \mathbf{v}_2 as the only non-vanishing component of the damage vector resulting in a significant simplification in the problem, there will still be eight independent damage related material constants (DRMCs) that needs to be determined before the constitutive relationship can be applied. These constants as material properties are difficult to measure, let alone the availability of any standard testing methodology. In [4], it was attempted to carry out ideal experiments as a classic means in physics to determined most of these DRMCs. Ideal experiments are carried out under idealised conditions. However, this is not necessarily to be any more inaccurate than a physical test where results can be affected by a lot of uncertainties. The basic considerations of these ideal experiments are the fact that many of the properties of a UD composite with a single array of microcracks parallel to fibres will remain affected if the microcracks are assumed to be mathematical cracks and perfectly closed before loading. These would offer some conditions. Mathematically, these conditions can be expressed in terms of a set of simultaneous equations. The solution of them leads to the determination of seven out of eight DRMCs and they can be expressed in terms of conventional elastic properties of the virgin material. If one introduces

$$\omega = \lambda \nu_2^2 = \frac{E_2^0 - E_2}{E_2^0} \quad (7)$$

where λ is a proportion factor which determines the magnitude of the damage variable \mathbf{v} as it was not fix in its original definition. It will appear in all the DRMCs but eventually absorbed when a more direct

By then, as far as the problem of a single array of microcracks in a UD composite is concerned, the damage representation has been formulated completely and rationally. However, before the formulated damage representation can be made of any practical applications, it needs to be furnished with an appropriate damage evolution law.

3 Damage Evolution

3.1 Damage driving forces

Damage representation of CDM is relatively a well-developed subject. The development as outline in the previous section, while moving the theory a step closer to its practical applications, does not result in any breakthrough. Its capability of being applied to predict the process of damage when the material is under an increasing level or duration of loading relies on the availability of an appropriate damage evolution law. A review of the state-of-the-art on the topic of damage evolution may reveal the fact that it is a rather underdeveloped subject where the practice has been mainly based on some kind of *ad hoc* approaches one way or another. The rationality has been limited to the fact that the derivatives of the Helmholtz free energy with respect to damage give rise to the so-called damage driving forces, there has been little rational discussion about the nature of such forces, while such forces had been employed in a number of theories, almost purely on an *ad hoc* basis. It is a perfectly valid statement that empirical relationships play a key role in the formulation of a damage evolution law. However, it is imperative to understand how far rationalism can go and where it should be met by empiricism. An account is presented below as a first attempt into this problem while keeping the problem to a single array of microcracks parallel to fibre.

The damage driving force vector can be obtained by differentiate the Helmholtz free energy with respect to the damage vector.

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{v} \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{cases} R_1 \\ R_2 \\ R_3 \end{cases} = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & W_{12} & W_{13} \\ W_{21} & W_{22} & W_{23} \\ W_{31} & W_{32} & W_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{cases} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{W} is a 2nd order tensor or a 3×3 matrix. R_i represents the force which drives the evolution of v_i . As only a single array of microcracks is concerned, v_2 is the only non-vanishing component in the damage vector \mathbf{v} as in the damage representation in

the previous section. w_{ij} represents the effect of the presence of v_j on R_i (the force driving v_i). Since v_1 and v_3 will not evolve, no matter how they are driven, the 1st and 3rd rows of \mathbf{W} will be of no relevance for the present study. Similarly, since v_1 and v_3 are always zero, the 1st and 3rd columns of \mathbf{W} will not contribute to the damage evolution. One is left a much simplified case to study, i.e.

$$R_2 = W_{22} v_2 \quad (12)$$

Given the fact that v_2 is the only contributing component, it is more convenient to use ω to represent the damage in agreement with the damage representation as in the previous section. Denote the relevant part of Helmholtz free energy as Ψ' , the corresponding damage driving force becomes

$$\rho = \frac{\partial \Psi'}{\partial \omega} = \frac{2}{\lambda} W_{22} \quad (13)$$

In general, W_{22} is independent of damage but a quadratic function of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, it can always be given in the following form.

$$W_{22} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (14)$$

where the components of \mathbf{D} can be expressed in terms of the DRMCs. Incidentally, all DRMCs involved in \mathbf{D} coincide those in \mathbf{C}^1 , i.e. $A_5, A_6, A_8, B_4, B_5, C_3, D_3$ and F_1 , which have been determined in the damage presentation as outline in the previous section. To summarise, the damage driving force in this case is a known quantity at a given state of damage and strain. To characterise the material, as far as the damage representation and damage driving forces are concerned, one only need conventional elastic constants while the DRMCs associated with the damage can be obtained from the elastic constants somehow.

In the literature, empiricism often kicks in as soon as the damage driving force is obtained. However, this may be a bit too soon. A simple observation is made in fracture mechanics that the critical total energy release rate is not a material constant as it varies with the modes of fracture, i.e. loading conditions. Defining the critical damage driving force as a material property to facilitate the damage evolution law may fall into the same type of mistake as taking the total critical energy release rate as a material property. The consequence would be inconsistency in the predicted results which in turn undermines the whole theoretical framework as a useful tool for engineering applications.

A close examination of matrix \mathbf{D} , one may find that it is a densely populated matrix. It is therefore hard to proceed much further directly. The following manipulations make a significant difference. From the damage representation, one has already obtained the stress-strain relationship (4) with damage incorporated in the stiffness matrix. The inverse of the relationship can be given as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{S}\boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{S} is the compliance of the damaged material which has been obtained in [4] as

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1^0} & & & & & \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & \frac{1}{E_2^0(1-\omega)} & & & & \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} & -\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0} & \frac{1}{E_2^0} & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}^0 \left(1 - \frac{1}{2(1+\nu_{23}^0)}\omega\right)} & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}^0} & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}^0(1-k\omega)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Using the compliance above, one can re-express W_{22} as follows.

$$W_{22} = \frac{\lambda}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \mathbf{S} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{\lambda}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{S} \quad (18)$$

bearing in mind of the symmetry of \mathbf{S} .

Carrying out the matrix multiplication and neglecting high order terms of ω , one obtains the following expression for \mathbf{H} .

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & P_I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & P_{III} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & P_{II} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{where } \begin{aligned} P_I &= P_I^0 + P_I^1 \omega \\ P_{II} &= P_{II}^0 + P_{II}^1 \omega \\ P_{III} &= P_{III}^0 + P_{III}^1 \omega \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

and P_I^0 , P_I^1 , P_{II}^0 , P_{II}^1 , P_{III}^0 and P_{III}^1 are all independent of damage as well as strain and they can be expressed in terms of elastic constants of the virgin material somehow. It has by then transpired that the damage driving force ρ is naturally partitioned into three modes squarely lined up with the three classic modes of fracture.

$$\rho = \rho_I + \rho_{II} + \rho_{III} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{where } \begin{aligned} \rho_I &= P_I \sigma_2^2 \\ \rho_{II} &= P_{II} \tau_{12}^2 \\ \rho_{III} &= P_{III} \tau_{23}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

It is now convenient to borrow the concept of fracture mechanics by considering the damage evolution along the line of crack propagation in fracture mechanics. The only difference is that the mode II and mode III are interchangeable here depending on the location of the crack front one is looking at. For crack front propagating along the direction of fibre, P_{II}^0 and P_{II}^1 happens to correspond to mode II, while P_{III}^0 and P_{III}^1 mode III. On the other hand, when the propagation in the direction transverse to fibres is concerned, they would be just wrong way around. This should not really matter if one understands that mode II and III may only be a kind of symbolism here.

3.2 Critical damage driving forces

Based on the established theory of fracture mechanics, there is a good reason to believe that critical damage driving forces ρ_I^c , ρ_{II}^c and ρ_{III}^c are material properties which should be obtained individually when a damaged material is tested under uniaxial stress state σ_{22} , τ_{12} and τ_{23} . It is obvious that other stress components will not affect the damage and this is in perfect agreement with the rational derivation above.

In terms of experimental measurements of critical damage driving forces ρ_I^c , ρ_{II}^c and ρ_{III}^c , the strategy as employed in fracture mechanics for critical energy release rates might be followed closely. The differences are (1) distributed damage in the specimen instead of a pre-planted crack; (2) the formula of damage driving force to be used instead of that of the energy release rate. As usual, one would expect those under shear loading challenging. However, this has been categorised as future development beyond this paper.

When the material is subjected to a stress state with combined σ_{22} , τ_{12} and τ_{23} , one may have to devise a mixed mode law in order to determine a critical state when damage start to evolve. Without losing generality, assuming a mixed mode criterion as follows.

$$\left(\frac{\rho_I}{\rho_I^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{II}}{\rho_{II}^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{III}}{\rho_{III}^c}\right)^m < 1 \quad (23)$$

When the above condition is satisfied, damage will not evolve. Otherwise, evolution is expected.

Assuming the condition of evolution is met by a set of ρ_I^0, ρ_{II}^0 and ρ_{III}^0 , i.e.

$$\left(\frac{\rho_I^0}{\rho_I^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{II}^0}{\rho_{II}^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{III}^0}{\rho_{III}^c}\right)^m = 1 \quad (24)$$

The total damage driving force

$$\rho^0 = \rho_I^0 + \rho_{II}^0 + \rho_{III}^0 \quad (25)$$

may not be a constant for a material as it may vary with the loading condition in general.

3.3 Damage evolution law

Once the critical condition is met, whether it is under a pure mode or a mixed mode, the damage state is expected to evolve. The evolution should be governed by an appropriate damage evolution law. Unfortunately, there does not seem to have a unique way of formulating a damage evolution law. Empirical approach may have to be resorted to.

One of the approaches as adopted in several accounts, e.g. [5], is to introduce the concept of damage surface which is similar to the concept of yield surface in plasticity. An incremental damage evolution law can then be derived in a similar way to that in the incremental theory of plasticity. However, there is a subtle difference there. A stress state on the yield surface is reachable as the domain inside the yield surface is a closed domain in a mathematical term, while a state on the damage surface may not be reachable due to the brittle nature of composites in general. Mathematically, the domain inside the damage surface is an open domain. Further derivation of a damage evolution law on the damage surface might leave a little doubt behind.

An alternative approach is based on the use of damage driving forces. It is conceivable that damage should be related to the damage force.

$$\omega = \omega(\rho_I, \rho_{II}, \rho_{III}) \quad (26)$$

If the above relationship can be established, it will govern the evolution of the damage. However, there does not seem to have an established way of constructing such a relationship, in general.

A possible way forward would be described as follows. Image the critical state is met at a value of the damage driving force ρ^0 as given in (25). One can expand the function in (26) into a Taylor's series in the neighbourhood of the critical state at a given damage ω^0 with high order terms can be neglected.

$$\omega = \omega^0 + \mu_I(\rho_I - \rho_I^0) + \mu_{II}(\rho_{II} - \rho_{II}^0) + \mu_{III}(\rho_{III} - \rho_{III}^0) + \dots \quad (27)$$

where μ_I, μ_{II} and μ_{III} are damage evolution related material constants and they will have to be determined empirically through experiments.

It is conceivable that the measurements of these constants can be incorporated in the same tests as those for critical damage driving forces ρ_I^c, ρ_{II}^c and ρ_{III}^c . A possible way of measuring critical damage driving forces ρ_I^c, ρ_{II}^c and ρ_{III}^c and damage evolution related material constants μ_I, μ_{II} and μ_{III} can be envisaged as follows.

Introduce a certain level of damage in a specimen, e.g. by loading up appropriately to generate microcracks, one can apply macroscopically uniaxial stress state σ_{22}, τ_{12} and τ_{23} , respectively, to grow the damage within an appropriate and small range with a number of increments. At each increment, the magnitude of damage ω can be evaluated. The damage driving forces ρ_I, ρ_{II} and ρ_{III} can be calculated, given the stress and the damage state. When the obtained data are plotted in an ω - ρ curve, it can be line fitted to give the corresponding μ as the slope of the fitted straight line, while the value of ρ at the intersection of the fitted straight line with the ρ axis should give the critical value of the corresponding damage drive force.

Once one can determine these critical damage driving forces ρ_I^c, ρ_{II}^c and ρ_{III}^c and damage evolution related material constants μ_I, μ_{II} and μ_{III} , a practical damage evolution law will have been constructed.

3.4 Incremental constitutive relationship

It can be noted that as the damage evolves under varying stress, the damage and stress states will gradually drift away from ρ^0 . One will have to keep updating the critical state. This process favours an incremental algorithm naturally. According to a well-established conclusion in plasticity, the irreversibility as is the nature of damage process also demands an incremental theory. An incremental CDM model can be obtained as

$$\Delta\sigma = (C^0 - C'\omega)\Delta\varepsilon - C'\varepsilon\Delta\omega \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta\omega = \mu_I\Delta\rho_I + \mu_{II}\Delta\rho_{II} + \mu_{III}\Delta\rho_{III} \quad (29)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho_I + \Delta\rho_I}{\rho_I^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{II} + \Delta\rho_{II}}{\rho_{II}^c}\right)^m + \left(\frac{\rho_{III} + \Delta\rho_{III}}{\rho_{III}^c}\right)^m = 1 \quad (30)$$

One needs to monitor the value of $\Delta\omega$. When it returns a negative value, an unloading conditions is signified and (29) should then be replaced by

$$\Delta\omega = 0. \quad (31)$$

The above should effectively define a material model which can be incorporated into structural analysis of composites to predict the structural behaviour involving damage distributed and evolving within the material of the structure. The actual implementation will be the subject of a future study to be published in due course.

4 Conclusion

The present paper extends a recent study of the representation of damage in the framework of CDM, where damage related materials constants (DRMCs) were determined through ideal experiments assisted with numerical experiments, into the aspect of damage evolution. The mode of damage has been intentionally kept to one of the simplest forms, i.e. a single array of microcracks orientated in a common direction transverse to the fibres in a UD composite. As in the damage representation, the rationality in the formulation of the damage evolution law has been the major concern, in particular, the boundary of rationality. It is clear that empiricism is inevitable in the construction of a damage evolution law. An effort has been made in this paper to identify the meeting point of rationality and empiricism. The purpose of this is to guide development of damage theories as well as the necessary experimental programme to facilitate such a theory. A possible approach along this direction has also been suggested in this paper where an incremental form of the constitutive relationship is illustrated with damage evolution incorporated. The application of such material model into appropriate material models for practical structural analysis with the damage process incorporated as a part of the analysis will be pursued in future publications.

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